

Modeling the Property Evolution of Cyanate Ester with Crosslinking, Strain-rate, and Temperature

Sagar Patil

Research Engineer

Michigan Technological University

spatil4@mtu.edu

CMMR Lab™

COMPUTATIONAL MECHANICS
& MATERIALS RESEARCH

Polymer-matrix Composites for deep space exploration

Cyanate Ester as a matrix material for PMCs

- Reactive cyanate group (-O-C≡N)
- High glass transition temperature
 - >200°C
- Low coefficient of thermal expansion
 - < 1 ppm/°C
- Low moisture absorption
 - < 1%
- High mechanical properties
 - tensile strength = 57 Mpa
 - stiffness = 4.3 GPa

Three cyanate ester molecules reacts to form **triazine ring**

Cure-induced Residual Stresses in PMCs

Cure cycle for epoxy

A: Point on the surface ply
 B: Point at an interior ply

Process dependent properties

Residual stress build-up during cure

Microcracks

Cracking due to thermal degradation and shrinkage

In-situ matrix properties different from neat resin

Zimmermann, K., et al., *Compos part B* (2010), 41: p. 326-336

Proposed Process Modeling Framework

Kashmari, K., et al., *ACS Polymers Au*, 2025, DOI: 10.1021/acspolymersau.5c00022

Objective

Utilize Molecular Dynamics to simulate virtual crosslinking and testing to predict thermo-mechanical property evolution

Build

AroCy XU371

Simulate

Virtual Crosslinking
Tensile tests

REACTOR

Analyze

Mass Density
Volumetric Shrinkage
Elastic Modulus
Yield Strength

f (crosslinking,
processing temperature)

Build

- LUNAR*
- Polymer Consistent Force Field – Interface Force Field (PCFF-IFF)**
- 360 monomers
- 15,840 atoms
- 3 replicates

AroCy XU371

Cell Builder to Randomize
Initial density: 0.18 g/cm³

Densify to target value of 1.2 g/cm³
Timestep: 1 fs
Sim. Time: 4 ns
NVT Ensemble
300 K

Equilibration
Timestep: 1 fs
Sim. Time: 2 ns
NPT Ensemble
300 K, 1 atm
Uncrosslinked density:
1.2038 ± 0.0008

■	C	Carbon
■	N	Nitrogen
■	O	Oxygen
□	H	Hydrogen

*Kempainen, J., et al., *J. Chem. Inf. Model*, 2024, 64 (13), 5
Heinz, H., et al.,
**Langmuir (2013), 29(6): p. 1754-1765
108-5126

Simulate

- LUNAR
- REACTER*
- 2 step reaction
 - I. initiation
 - II. triazine formation
- 20 reactions
 - 40 sets of templates

Crosslinking Sim.
Timestep: 0.1 fs
Sim. Time: 2 ns
NVT Ensemble
550 K

Equilibration 1
Timestep: 1 fs
Sim. Time: 2 ns
NPT Ensemble
300 K, 1 atm

Crosslinking degree (%) , $\phi = \frac{\text{No. of triazine groups formed}}{\text{Max.no of triazine groups}}$

*Gissinger, J. R., et al., *Macromolecules* (2020) 53 : p. 9953-9961

Simulate

- LUNAR
- REACTER
- Convert to Reactive Interface Force Field (IFF-R)*
- Morse bonds for tensile deformation

$$E_{morse} = D[1 - e^{-\alpha(r-r_0)}]^2$$

B →

Annealing
Timestep: 1 fs
Sim. Time: 4 ns
600 K to 300 K at 75 K/ns
NVT Ensemble

Equilibration 2
Timestep: 1 fs
Sim. Time: 2 ns
NPT Ensemble
300 K, 1 atm

Tensile in x, y & z directions
Timestep: 1 fs
Strain-rate: 2×10^8 /s, strain: 15%
Sim. Time: 0.75 ns
NPT Ensemble
300 K, 1 atm

*Winetrout, J. J., et al., *Nat Commun* (2024), 1 (15): p. 7945

Analyze

mass density = average (last 500 ps from LAMMPS output)

post – gelation volumetric shrinkage at $\phi = \frac{V_{\phi} - V_{\phi=gel\ point}}{V_{\phi=gel\ point}}$

Mechanical properties =

- LUNAR
- RFR-method for tensile simulations*
- f (crosslinking, processing temperature)

*Kempainen, J., et al., *Understanding and Interpreting Stress-Strain Curves from Molecular Dynamics Simulation of Amorphous Polymers*. ChemRxiv. 2025; This content is a preprint and has not been peer-reviewed.

Mass Density

Gel point

Post-gelation volumetric shrinkage

Young's Modulus vs Temperature

Young's Modulus vs Strain-rate at 27°C

Yield Strength vs Temperature

Yield Strength vs Strain-rate at 27°C

Summary

- **PCFF-IFF and REACTER was implemented to predict the properties**
- **Young's modulus and yield strength of cyanate ester**
 - increases with crosslinking
 - decreases with temperature
 - strain-rate has no significant effect
- **Build comprehensive set of material property dataset**
- **Thermal simulations:**
 - Glass transition temperature
 - Coefficient of thermal expansion
 - Conductivity
 - Viscosity

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- Superior HPC, Michigan Tech
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- Michigan Technological University

CMMR Lab

COMPUTATIONAL MECHANICS
& MATERIALS RESEARCH

AFRL

Molecular Dynamics

1. Molecular structure
2. Initial position and velocities of atoms
3. Force Field

Input

Output

1. Mechanical properties
2. Interaction energy and Friction
3. Contact angle

$$E_{total} = \underbrace{\sum E_{bond} + \sum E_{angle} + \sum E_{torsion}}_{Bonded} + \underbrace{\sum E_{vdw} + \sum E_{coulombic}}_{Non-bonded}$$

LAMMPS : Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator

Li, C., Strachan, A., *J. Polym. Sci. B*, (2014) 53: p. 103-122

Valavala, P. K., Odegard, G.M., *Rev. Adv. Mater. Sci.*, (2005) 9: p. 34-44

Free volume analysis

Reactive Interface Force Field

b IFF $E_{\text{harmonic-bond}} = K_{r,ij}(r_{ij} - r_{0,ij})^2$

1) $E_{\text{Morse-bond}} = D_{ij}[1 - e^{-\alpha_{ij}(r_{ij}-r_{0,ij})}]^2$

IFF-R 2) $E_{\text{Morse-bond}} = D_{ij}[1 - e^{-\alpha_{ij}(r_{ij}-r_{0,ij})}]^2 - D_{ij}$

c

Parameter	Interpretation	Measurement/data source
$r_{0,ij}$	Equilibrium bond length between atoms i, j	Microwave spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction
α	Bond vibration constant (width)	Infrared and Raman spectroscopy
D	Bond dissociation energy	Thermochemical data from experiments or quantum calculations

IFF = Interface Force Field

IFF-R = Reactive Interface Force Field

What is Free Volume

$$V_{System} = V_{Free} + V_{Atom}$$

- User Inputs:**
- voxel_size
 - **probe**_{radii}
 - **vdw**_{radii}

DETDA Monomer

Free volume analysis results

Density	: 0.01202 g/cm ³
Simulation cell volume	: 24620.2 A ³
Atom volume	: 327.96 A ³
Free volume	: 24292.28 A ³
Percent Free volume	: 98.7 %

Atom Volume

Fractional Free Volume

Fractional atom Volume

Fractional Free Volume

Mass Density at processing temp.

Preliminary Results for crosslinked model

Property	Units	Predictions	Experiments
ρ	g/cm ³	1.255 ± 0.009	1.28 ± 0.01
E	GPa	4.49 ± 0.23	3.55 ± 0.27
ν	-	0.332**	
σ	MPa	97.43 ± 18.02	59.58 ± 5.34*
T_g	°C	259.16 ± 70.34	254.5 (DMA)
CTE below T_g	µm/°C	0.480 ± 0.047	0.224 ± 0.035
CTE above T_g	µm/°C	0.802 ± 0.111	0.249 ± 0.011

*Ultimate Tensile Strength

Post-gelation volumetric shrinkage

Crosslinking simulation

Analyze

- Crosslinking simulation for XU371 (360 monomers)

rxn 1: initiation
rxn 2: triazine formation

Rep	Probability		No. of reactions		Max. Extent of Cure (%)	Simulation time (nanoseconds)
	rxn 1	rxn 2	rxn 1	rxn 2		
d1	0.1	0.9	430	209	58.05	0.705
	0.01	0.9	392	284	78.88	1.795
	0.001	0.9	360	331	91.94	2.005
	0.0001	0.9	355	328	91.11	2.005

Rep	No. of reactions		Max. Extent of Cure (%)	Simulation time (nanoseconds)
	rxn 1	rxn 2		
d1	355	328	91.11	2.005
d2	359	328	91.11	2.005
d3	355	325	90.27	2.005
d4	356	328	91.11	2.005
d5	358	332	92.22	2.005

Gel point

Preliminary Tg Results for crosslinked model

Property	cooling	heating
1	8.25	326.99
2	2.52	210.64
3	249.75	344.55
4	183.38	212.62
5	248.16	201.02
Std. avg	138.41 ± 124.36	259.16 ± 70.34

Property	rate	cooling	heating
1	50	8.25	326.99
	25	104.44	138.22

Property	rate	cooling	heating
1	50	8.25	326.99
	50 before ann	150.09	236.31

* Cecil Evers, FSU

Update: d1_npt_2.995_inter_0.0001_0.9_800K

Inter: different monomers
 Intra: same monomers

Crosslinking sims

Mass Density at room temp.

Analyze

- Crosslinking simulation for XU371 (360 monomers)
- RFR-method for tensile sims

mass density = average (last 500 ps from LAMMPS output)
gel point = inflection (molecular mass of largest molecular cluster)
= peak (molecular mass of second – largest molecular cluster)
= peak (Reduced average molecular weight (RMW))

$$\text{post – gelation volumetric shrinkage at } \phi = \frac{V_{\phi} - V_{\phi=\text{gel point}}}{V_{\phi=\text{gel point}}}$$

Kemppainen, J., et al., *Understanding and Interpreting Stress-Strain Curves from Molecular Dynamics Simulation of Amorphous Polymers*. ChemRxiv. 2025; This content is a preprint and has not been peer-reviewed.

Regression Fringe Response Modulus Method

- Tensile simulations using class2-xe Force Field*
- Automated processing* of Stress-Strain data (QR code)

1. Low pass filter of MD data
2. Algorithm to determine linear elastic region
3. Algorithm to find yield point
4. Process full array of 3 directions-5 replicates-many DoC-many Temps
5. Determine outliers

*Methodologies not published yet, 2 papers submitted

MD details

- **Software Package** – LAMMPS
- **Number of atoms** – 16,682
- **Total replicates** = 5

Bulk Modulus

- **NPT ensemble** – 1 atm, 1 ns
- **NPT ensemble** – 5000 atm, 1 ns

Shear Modulus

- **Strain rate** – $2 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$
- **Maximum strain** – 15%

Glass Transition Temperature and CTE

- **Cooling** – 700 K to 100 K
- **Cooling rate** – 50 K/ns

Young's Modulus
Poisson's ratio
Yield Strength

Toray 3900

- Carbon
- Oxygen
- Nitrogen
- Hydrogen

Reactive Interface Force field (IFF-R)

- Enables bond breaking via Morse potential
- Computationally efficient (50× faster than ReaxFF)
- Requires single set of parameters

$$E_{morse} = D[1 - e^{-\alpha(r-r_0)}]^2$$

Winetrout, J. J., et al., *Nat Commun* (2024), 1 (15): p. 7945
Heinz, H., et al., *Langmuir* (2013), 29(6): p. 1754-1765

Strain-rate Compensation

The MD predicted mechanical properties are corrected for viscous response or the strain-rate effect

Patil et al., *Soft Matter*, 19 (35): p. 6731-6742 (2023)

Effect of Strain rate on Young's modulus predicted via MD

Odegard, G. M., et al., *Macromolecules*, 54 (2021), p. 9815–9824

Effect of Strain rate on yield strength predicted via MD

Odegard, G. M., et al., *Macromolecules*, 54 (2021), p. 9815–9824

Young's Modulus as a function of strain rate

Odegard, G. M., et al., *Macromolecules*, 54 (2021), p. 9815–9824

Yield Strength as a function of strain rate

Odegard, G. M., et al., *Macromolecules*, 54 (2021), p. 9815–9824

Comparison of Predicted Young's Modulus using (G,K) pair and tensile test

Patil, S. U., et al., *arXiv/cond-mat.mtrl-sci* 2021, 2108.00933

Comparison of Predicted Yield Strength using (G,K) pair and tensile test

Patil, S. U., et al., *arXiv/cond-mat.mtrl-sci* 2021, 2108.00933

Bulk modulus prediction is highly sensitive to small changes in Poisson's ratio

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Bulk modulus prediction is highly sensitive to small changes in Poisson's ratio

For $G = 1$ GPa,

$$K = \frac{2G(1+\nu)}{3(1-2\nu)}$$

ν	K (GPa)
0.4	4.66667
0.49	49.66667
0.499	499.66667
0.4999	4999.66667
0.49999	49999.66667

Shenogina, N. B., et al., *Polymer 54* (2013), p. 3370-3376

Read Dr. Anoush Poursartip's work to learn more about this approach.

Post-gelation volumetric shrinkage

Preliminary Tg Results for crosslinked model

* Cecil Evers, FSU

Molecular Dynamics

Simulation box

1. Molecular structure
2. Initial position and velocities of atoms
3. Force Field

Input

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1. Mechanical properties
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$$E_{total} = \underbrace{\sum E_{bond} + \sum E_{angle} + \sum E_{torsion}}_{Bonded} + \underbrace{\sum E_{vdw} + \sum E_{coulombic}}_{Non-bonded}$$

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Polymer-matrix Composites for High-temperature applications

<https://www.cf-composites.toray/products/thermoset/others/resins.html>

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